

IN THE FOOTSTEPS OF SOCIETAL TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Migration is the act of relocating people from the places where they were born, raised or lived to spend part or all of their lives for various reasons. Urbanization is the process of employment and production moving away from agricultural and rural activities and towards industry and service sectors, starting about 5,000 years ago in Mesopotamia.

While migration movements around the world shape the urbanization process and architecture, an important component of these processes has been the experiences and participation of women. Migration causes people to move to different places and often accelerates the process of urbanization. In this process, women attract attention with their social roles, needs and impact on architecture. The relationship between migration, urbanization, women and architecture represents an important transformation.

This research focuses on the roles of women in migration processes, the difficulties and opportunities they experience with urbanization, their reflections on architecture and their role in social transformation. How the change experienced by women with migration and urbanization can be addressed in the context of architecture and urban planning, women's experiences in these processes and their effects on social transformation constitute the main themes of the article. In this context, the roles of architecture and women in the process of social transformation are examined and discussed in the field of social equality and urban planning.

Key words: migration, urbanization, architecture, women, women's role, women's experience

INTRODUCTION

While migration movements around the world shape the urbanization process and architecture, an important component of these processes has been the experiences and participation of women. Migration causes people to move to different places and often accelerates the urbanization process. In this process, women attract attention with their social roles, needs and impact on architecture.

When the effects of the migration process on urbanization are examined, it is generally seen that social problems and gender differences are not sufficiently focused on. The specific challenges experienced by migrating women require an in-depth assessment of how gender roles and expectations are shaped during the migration process. Women have a different impact on the dynamics of migration and urbanization. Migration can carry women to different geographical regions and cause them to struggle to survive in new settlements. Women may encounter reshaping of their social roles in the places they migrate to there. For example, their participation in the labor market or their domestic and social roles may vary depending on the conditions in the place of migration. Especially with the rapid expansion of cities, the need for housing increases and

architects design new housing models to meet these needs. Women play an important role in housing design and urban planning.

While migration and urbanization affect women's daily lives and needs, architecture must also adapt to this change. Women's needs in matters such as safety, accessibility and public transportation should be taken into consideration in the design and architectural planning of cities. The relationship between migration, urbanization, women and architecture reflects the transformation of not only physical structures but also social structures. In this process, women's experiences and needs play a critical role in designing and building more inclusive and livable cities.

Considering the gender perspective and understanding the specific needs of migrating women when assessing the effects of migration on the urbanization process allows the development of more comprehensive and fair policies and programs. In this context, enriching research on migration and urbanization with gender-based analyzes can contribute to finding more effective solutions.

MIGRATION

Definition of the Concept of Migration

Migration is generally the movement of people from one place to another and the permanent or temporary change of living place because of this change of place. Migration can occur for many different reasons; various factors such as economic, social, political, environmental or cultural factors may lead people to migrate.

Migration usually occurs from a source location to a destination location. This mobility can occur at the level of individuals, families or communities. Migrants can settle temporarily or permanently in the place they migrate to. Immigration can cause social, economic and cultural changes. In addition, the concept of migration can affect the dynamics of both the migrants and the place they migrate to there. Types of migration include internal migration and international migration. While internal migration occurs between different regions within a country, international migration refers to the movement of people from one country to another. Migration is an important social phenomenon that affects the structure, culture and economy of societies.

Migration refers to the situation of people moving from their current location to another location for economic, political and cultural reasons, which is observed in every period of history and in every society (Koçak and Terzi, 2012). Migration can be defined as the act of geographically relocating people from one place to another in order to spend all or part of their lives in the future, either completely or temporarily (Akkayan, 1979).

Causes of Migration

Migration is an action that has various depths in the fabric of human history. The reasons behind this action have a complex network that causes people to leave the places where they were born and raised and move towards different geographies. Economic reasons, the search for income opportunities, efforts to find a job and economic inequalities are among the main driving forces of migration. Political pressures, wars and human rights violations are also among the factors that cause people to turn to other places. While environmental problems caused by natural disasters and climate change can also affect migration decisions, social reasons, family reunification, educational opportunities and the search for better living conditions are some of the factors that trigger migration. This complexity reveals the root causes of migration as a multifaceted and impressive phenomenon that has a profound impact on people's lives, cultural structures and social dynamics.

“The most obvious reason for internal migration in the 1950s was industrialization and development. The presence of education and health groups in cities and the attractiveness of city life have made cities very attractive. For this reason, population movement from rural areas to cities has begun to gain momentum.” (Tüfekçi, 2002).

"Generally, in theories explaining migration, it is mentioned that the place to live has "pushing" qualities and the place to migrate has "attractive" qualities when making the decision to migrate (Buz, 2009).

If we proceed based on Buz's words, we can list the push and pull reasons.

Pushing reasons can be considered as economic difficulties, political pressures, environmental problems, social and cultural pressures. If we explain these reasons;

- Factors such as economic difficulties, inadequate job opportunities, income inequality and unemployment may direct people to other places.
- Reasons such as political pressures, wars, political instability, and human rights violations may force people to leave their places.
- Factors such as environmental problems, natural disasters, climate change and environmental pollution may cause migration from the place of residence.
- Social and cultural pressures, discrimination, social pressures, cultural conflicts, difficulties arising from religious or ethnic affiliation may also encourage migration.

Attractive reasons can be considered as job and economic opportunities, education and health services, quality of life, social and family ties, cultural and artistic diversity. If we explain these reasons;

- Economic advantages such as business and economic opportunities, employment opportunities, better job opportunities, and high income potential make the place to migrate attractive.
- Education and health services, quality education opportunities and places with good health services can increase the attractiveness of the new place to migrate.
- Factors such as quality of life, better living conditions, a safe environment, cultural diversity, and the presence of social services attract people to a particular place.
- Social and family ties, family reunification, and the presence of social support networks can increase the attractiveness of a place with familiar or family members.
- Cultural and artistic diversity, places where cultural activities are intense, where artistic activities take place and where there is cultural diversity can attract people.

When the situations in question are evaluated, push factors can be important factors that push people to move away from the place and environment they live in and affect their decisions to migrate. In addition, pull factors are factors that make migrating to a region attractive and cause people to choose to live in a new place. The advantages and living conditions offered by the place to migrate are important factors that affect people's decisions to migrate.

Effects and Consequences of Migration

Migration can lead to economic changes in both the destination and the destination. While the labor force may decrease from the place of migration, the demand for labor may increase in the places of migration. This can either support or hinder economic growth by affecting the job market.

Migration can change the demographic structure of a region. Immigration can affect the average age and cause the population to increase or decrease.

Cultural diversity increases as a result of different cultures coming together in the place of migration. New cultural interactions and exchanges may occur. Food, art and language are enriched. Social interactions and adaptation processes may occur between migrating people and the local population. This can lead to social changes.

Large-scale migrations can seriously impact the use of natural resources, environmental sustainability and urban planning. High population movements can increase the rate of consumption of natural resources and disrupt the environmental balance. In addition, these migrations may also change urban planning by affecting the infrastructure of cities, housing demand and service needs.

URBANIZATION

Definition of the Concept of Urbanization

Urbanization is generally defined as the increasing tendency of the population to live in cities by concentrating from rural areas to cities.

Urbanization; As a result of migration to rural areas for various reasons, on the one hand, the growth of existing cities in terms of population and area, and on the other hand, the growth of villages, towns, etc. The gradual growth of settlements, eventually turning into cities, and the number of existing cities increasing (Nadaoğlu,1996).

In this process, people generally move away from agriculture and rural life and settle in cities to seek job opportunities in the industrial, commercial and service sectors. Urbanization may also be due to the increase in services and facilities offered in cities, such as infrastructure, housing, education and healthcare. Urbanization generally causes economic, social, cultural and environmental changes and significantly affects the population distribution and structure in a region. This process is also considered a part of modernization and social transformation.

Wirth defined the city as "the presence of socially uniform people settled together in a relatively large area, densely and permanently."

Reasons for Urbanization

According to Keleş (1996), the reasons for urbanization are stated as economic, technological, political and socio-psychological.

Reasons for urbanization may vary depending on the economic, social, cultural and environmental dynamics of a region. These factors often encourage urbanization by increasing migration from rural areas to cities. For example, economic factors such as the industrialization process in an economy, a decrease in agricultural production, changes in job opportunities or income differences may cause people to migrate from rural areas to cities.

Socially, Better education opportunities offered in cities, improvements in health services or a stronger social infrastructure may also increase the tendency towards cities.

Culturally, Factors such as cultural diversity in cities, artistic events, and the liveliness of the entertainment industry may also affect people's choice of city life.

Environmentally, risks in regions where natural disasters occur frequently, the difficulty of environmental sustainability or the intensity of environmental problems may also accelerate migration from rural areas to cities. All these factors generally contribute to people's migration towards cities and urbanization. This process may vary depending on the character, economic structure and social structure of the region.

Women In The Framework Of Migration, Urbanization And Architecture

Women's Role and Experiences in the Migration Process

The roles and experiences of women in the migration process is an important area of research in social sciences, and this subject generally focuses on the difficulties experienced by immigrant women, the obstacles they face and the struggles they go through. Migration refers to mobility from one society to another due to various factors such as economic, political, environmental or social reasons.

Migrant women generally maintain their families' social and emotional support systems during this process, while also taking on roles such as child care, education and social solidarity. The migration process is full of many difficulties for women. First of all, factors such as language barriers and cultural adaptation problems affect the integration process of immigrant women into new societies. This may increase the risk of employment difficulties and discrimination within society. In some cases, immigrant women may be marginalized and ostracized in society. However,

women who migrate also show great resilience. Their efforts to adapt to new societies, their efforts to create social networks, and their efforts to achieve success in various fields highlight the important contributions and experiences of women in the migration process. Women develop various strategies to strengthen themselves and their families and play an important role in the process of adapting to their new society.

This situation provides an important opportunity for migration policies and social integration strategies to be more effective and inclusive. Gender-focused approaches can help create more equitable and supportive policies that take into account the needs and experiences of migrating women. Developing policies that support women's empowerment, their access to resources, and their ability to take on more active roles in society can facilitate the integration process of immigrant women and make societies more inclusive. This is an important focus for studies in the social sciences to understand immigrant women's experiences and support policy recommendations in this area.

Women's Role and Experiences in the Urbanization Process

The role of women in the urbanization process makes significant contributions to the socio-economic fabric of urbanization. In this evolutionary process, women generally migrate from rural areas to cities, their participation in the workforce increases and they tend to find jobs in different sectors. Job opportunities in cities can strengthen women's economic independence and promote their social mobility. However, women face various difficulties in urban life.

Women may be obliged to fulfill their family obligations during the urbanization process. Additionally, during the urbanization process, women may move away from their families and be deprived of social support networks. Among other negative effects that women are exposed to during the urbanization process, they may face many negative experiences such as concerns about women's safety, sexual harassment and violence, workplace discrimination, low wages and poor working conditions. Lack of adequate housing and infrastructure problems can negatively affect women's lives. Additionally, migrating women may have difficulty adapting to their new environment and may face the risk of social exclusion.

According to Omelianuk (2003), "Urbanization does not always mean a negative experience for immigrant women. Some positive effects can be mentioned, especially for immigrant women who are economically disadvantaged. The urbanization process causes women's education levels to increase, the age of marriage to increase, and as a result, women start having children at older ages. It is also notable that women in urban areas generally have fewer children than women in rural areas. The main reason for this is that women entering the workforce choose to postpone having children or do not choose to have children."

Women's experiences in the urbanization process are important in terms of redefining gender roles, addressing social equality and women's rights issues. More support is needed by policy makers to ensure that women have access to better employment opportunities, benefit from educational opportunities and benefit equally from urban infrastructure. Women's experiences in urban areas can be taken into account in urban planning and policy-making processes and can contribute to the creation of more inclusive and fair societies. In this way, women can take a more active part in the urban transformation process and a more balanced structure can be formed in social change. The roles of women in the urbanization process and the effects of this process on women's lives are an important research topic to understand the structural structure of society and develop urban planning policies on the basis of gender equality.

The Role and Experiences of Migrant Women in Architecture and the Architectural Process

Migration is recognized as a complex phenomenon that requires a multidisciplinary approach to understand women's roles and experiences in architecture and the architectural process. Migration is a process that is generally evaluated together with cultural, economic and social dynamics, and in this context, architecture plays a decisive role in shaping this process.

Although architecture has generally been perceived as a male-dominated field throughout history, today the role and experiences of women in the architectural process are becoming increasingly evident. Women show an increasing success rate in terms of participation in architectural education and active participation in the professional field. Architecture is enriched through women's aesthetic understanding, functional design understanding and social perspectives. Women stand out with sensuality, sustainability and user-friendly solutions in the design of spaces. Additionally, women's leadership in the architectural process has the potential to create more inclusive and participatory spaces by increasing the diversity of projects.

Understanding how migrating women exist in spaces requires collaboration between both social sciences and architectural disciplines. The impact of women on the spaces where they migrate should be considered in a wide range of areas, from home design to public spaces. At this point, architects and social scientists should develop design principles that are sensitive to the needs of women, support intercultural interaction and observe gender equality.

Difficulties encountered during the migration process may affect the social position, economic situation and quality of life of migrating women. Women who migrate may often be exposed to gender norms, economic difficulties and cultural barriers. This may indicate a lack of a sensitive approach to the difficulties experienced by women in architectural processes and space designs. If spatial arrangements do not suit women's needs in terms of safety and access, this can negatively impact women's daily lives. Architecture can contribute to mitigating these challenges by creating safe, sustainable and inclusive spaces. In this context, it is important to consider architectural approaches in an integrated manner with social sciences in order to support the integration of immigrant women and to design in accordance with the principle of gender equality.

Greater representation and active participation of immigrant women in the field of architecture can increase spatial diversity and cultural richness. The involvement of women in architectural design and planning processes allows spaces to be richer and more diverse in terms of aesthetics and functionality. Additionally, this participation can be a step towards creating spaces that better meet the needs of women and achieving gender equality in the discipline of architecture.

Planning to Improve the Quality of Life of Migrant Women

Planning to improve the quality of life of migrant women is a priority element in sustainable and inclusive urban development strategies. These strategies aim to strengthen the economic, social and cultural integration of migrating women by giving priority to their special needs. In this context, when considered from a scientific perspective, it can be recommended that these strategies focus on the following basic points:

Adequate housing and infrastructure for migrating women: It is essential to provide safe, accessible and affordable housing to migrating women in order to improve the quality of life. Additionally, these residences should provide easy access to public spaces and basic services. Infrastructures such as public spaces, parks and public transportation systems that will facilitate women's daily lives should also be a priority in planning processes.

Education and Employment Opportunities: In order to improve the quality of life of immigrant women, plans focusing on education and employment opportunities should be developed. This should include training programs and employment support that enable women to develop their skills and integrate into the labor market.

Social Participation and Security: Planning should encourage immigrant women to participate more actively in social life and provide a safe environment in the city. Event spaces that support social interaction, cultural events, and increasing women's access to leadership roles can significantly impact quality of life.

Health Services: Sustainable planning should provide easily accessible health services that are suitable for the health needs of immigrant women. This should include services such as reproductive health, child care, general health check-up and psychosocial support.

Cultural Sensitivity and Diversity: Migrant women often come from different cultures. Planning should include cultural sensitivity training and activities to understand and respect this cultural diversity. This can improve the quality of life by making it easier for various groups in the city to live together.

These planning strategies to improve the quality of life of migrant women are of critical importance to ensure that women have a stronger position in society and allow them to fully use their potential in the city. Effective implementation of these strategies can contribute to the creation of more equitable, inclusive and sustainable cities.

CONCLUSION

Within the scope of this research, the relationship between migration, urbanization and architecture and the effects of these processes on women's lives were examined in detail. Migration is accepted as an act of relocation of people that includes not only a geographical change but also a cultural, social and economic transformation. Women, in particular, play an important role in this process of change in societies as an integral part of migration and urbanization. Women faced various difficulties during the migration process, but they also gained new opportunities.

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In this process, women's social roles, needs and participation are important elements that should be taken into account in shaping architectural designs and urban planning. Understanding the role of women in social transformation, architecture and urbanization processes and considering their experiences can contribute to the creation of more equitable, sustainable and inclusive cities.

It can be possible by developing policies and plans that encourage greater participation of women in social, economic and spatial terms. Architecture and space design should be an important part of urban planning and architectural policies based on gender equality, embracing the experiences of migrant women. In this context, encouraging women's active participation by taking into account migration and urbanization processes and understanding their needs and adapting designs according to these needs is a critical step to create more inclusive, accessible and sustainable spaces. With this approach, a more fair, supportive and safe environment can be provided for immigrant women.

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